

samples were stored at 20 °C and 75% relative humidity after infestation. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications.

Resistance was evaluated on three parameters: emerging adults, susceptibility index (SI), and weight loss. The emerging adults were removed each day and counted. Seed weight loss was calculated by weighing seed before and after the experiment.

SI was based on the formula

$$SI = \frac{\text{natural log number of emerging adults}}{\text{average development period}} \times 100$$

Susceptibility was scored as % emerging adults where resistant (R) = <10%, moderately resistant (MR) = 10-20%, and susceptible = >20%.

Twelve of 44 BPH-resistant rice varieties tested were rated R and 15 were MR to AGM (see table). The new variety Hong Yuan, which is a cross of the good agronomic variety Hong Zhan and resistant donor Suweon 294, is R to BPH and MR to AGM. Hong Yuan yielded an average 6 t/ha, indicating that the resistance was heritable and easily recombined with other agronomic traits. ■

Stress tolerance—excess water

Plant elongation at three seedling ages in some rice varieties

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Experiments using three seedling ages (2, 3, and 4 wk with 9, 21, and 21 entries, respectively) were laid out in a completely randomized design with three replications to assess variation in plant elongation ability induced by flooding. The objective was to select the most

appropriate seedling age for use in work on the genetics of elongation ability.

Seedlings were submerged for 7 d in 100 cm of water in a glasshouse tank. Plant height was recorded before and after flooding, and the difference was used to calculate plant elongation.

Seedlings in each age group survived. Entries differed significantly in plant elongation. Percent increase in elongation after flooding was highest in the 2-wk seedlings (see table), perhaps because older seedlings were taller than younger

ones and needed comparatively less elongation to survive at the 100-cm flooding depth. Leaf sheaths and blades contributed considerably to plant elongation (data not presented).

To compare the relevance of results, we used previous knowledge that IR11141-6-1-4 and IR11288-B-B-69-1 are elongating modern varieties (MVs), whereas IR36, IR42, BKNFR76106-16-0-1, and FR13A are nonelongating MVs. Better selection of elongating MVs and nonelongating MVs was obtained from the 4-wk treatment. The difference in average elongation between these groups was greater at 4 wk (6.3 cm) than at 3 wk (3.0 cm) (see table). ■

Plant elongation at 3 seedling ages following 7 d of submergence.

Variety	Plant elongation (cm) at			Elongation score in previous test
	2 wk	3 wk	4 wk	
Elongating types				
Saingar	-	37	13	1
Barogar	-	37	20	1
LMN111	-	42	21	1
Jalmagna	24	27	36	1
NDGR407	25	-	-	1
Chakia 59	-	34	16	3
IR40905-11-3-1-5-3-3	-	25	16	3
NC492	-	28	20	3
Baisbish	26	23	21	3
NDGR150	22	22	7	5
FRG15	-	24	9	5
Madhukar	-	20	10	5
NDGR207	15	21	12	5
Elongating MVs				
IR11141-6-1-4	17	16	12	5
IR28273-R-R-R-39-28	-	17	18	5
IR11288-B-B-69-1	13	12	11	5
Nonelongating MVs				
Ghoghari	-	18	10	7
Shayma	-	15	9	7
IR42 (susceptible check)	14	9	8	9
FR13A	-	13	5	9
BKNFR76106-16-0-1	-	8	5	9
IR36	11	9	7	9
Mean increase (%)	46.9	37.9	18.7	
CV (%)	9.2	17.6	25.0	

Optimum water depth for testing fast elongating deepwater rice (DWR) varieties

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We conducted an experiment to determine the optimum water depth for testing the ability for fast elongation in

Table 1. Analysis of variance for percent elongation in 12 varieties at 5 water depths and control.

SV	DF	MS ^a
Replications	2	32.0 ns
Water depth (d)	5	3013.1**
Error (a)	10	18.6
Varieties (v)	11	1861.0**
Depth × variety (d × v)	55	113.9**
Error (b)	132	17.8

CV (a) = 18.0%, CV (b) = 17.6%

** = significant at 1% level, ns = not significant.